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Case Report

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Clinical Case Review - First HoLEP using Lumenis. LTD patented MOSES technology at the First center in Iraq using the Lumenis. LTD high-power holmium laser system Pulse 120H with Moses technology

Duraïd Alhadithi

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Abstract

Introduction: In Iraq Dr. Duraïd Alhadithi Urologist at Al_Andulus urology clinic, has introduced a Holmium Laser Enucleation of the Prostate (HoLEP) service as the gold standard for the treatment of Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia (BPH).

Materials and Methods: The Al_Andulus urology clinic, Iraq, purchased the first Lumenis.LTD high power Holmium Laser Pulse 120H with Moses technology system and Dr. Duraïd Alhadithi said 'although we start using lasers in treating BPH lately, we decided to start from the top and nothing is better now than the Lumenis. LTD Pulse 120H with Moses technology for HoLEP'. The patient for this clinical case review is the 6th patient in the series of 10 treated using the HOLEP with MOSES technology technique at the Al_Andulus urology clinic, Iraq, he is a 68-year-old smoker, echocardiography study was good EJ F 58 with pre-clinical studies of;

- IPSS 26
- QoL 6
- Q max 8ml/sec
- PSA 2, 85 PSA is 2.85 ng/ml
- Prostate size 75ml by abdominal ultrasound with a middle lobe. And the digital rectal examination was of a uniformly enlarged firm prostate, median sulcus intact with no hard nodules.

Results: The patient had an operation time 75 minutes including 10 minutes of Morcellation with no significant blood loss and no drop-in hematocrit a hospital stay of 18 hours total with catheter removal early in morning and the patient passed urine twice before discharge.

Conclusion: In conclusion Dr. Duraïd Alhadithi Urologist at Al_Andulus urology clinic, Iraq 'After this surgery I believe that HOLEP with MOSES technology using the Lumenis.LTD Pulse 120H Holmium Laser System will be the gold standard method in treating prostates in Iraq due to many factors including minimal bleeding, minimal need for bladder irrigation post operatively, rapid recovery, early removal of catheter, and complete resection of the prostate gland comparing to traditional Trans Urethral Resection of the Prostate (TURP)'.

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